

Spectaors' Recall Level of Advertising and Sponsorships in the Broadcasts of Sports Competitions

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Keywords

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ABSTRACT

In the sports industry, advertisements and sponsorships made in order to create awareness and increase awareness on the masses / audiences provide serious contributions to the companies and the sponsored organization. In the study conducted to determine the duration and level of recall of these contributions, the levels of recall of advertising and sponsorship practices in the broadcasts of sports competitions by the audience were determined. The population of the study consists of all spectators who follow football, basketball, tennis, athletics and other sports competitions broadcast on television. The sample of the study consisted of 466 spectators who actively or passively follow sports competitions and can be reached easily. Personal information form and a questionnaire developed by the researcher were used as data collection tools. Computerized statistical methods were used to analyze the data. In addition to descriptive statistics, normality tests were applied before the analysis. In addition to arithmetic mean (\bar{x}), frequency (f) values, Chi-square test and z test for row-column comparison were used to analyze the data. As a result of the analysis, while there were differences between the variables of the recall of shoe and jersey brands, recall of pitch-side advertisements, recall of the last watched competition time and recall of stadium names in terms of the level of recall of advertising and sponsorship practices in the broadcasts of sports competitions, no difference was found in terms of other variables.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sponsorship, one of the most frequently used marketing communication tools today, provides resources in many areas such as companies, festivals, television channels, exhibitions, archaeological excavations, sports and music. Sponsorship, which is seen as one of the most effective communication and marketing methods that can be used to reach the target audience [1], is not an aid or philanthropy in the form of financial or material donation by thinking of others [2]. Because there are no expectations such as advertising and publicity in aid and charity activities. However, in sponsorship, short or long-term contributions are expected for the commercial success of the sponsoring company. In other words, sponsorship is an effort to create brand awareness, strengthen business and brand image, gain reputation in the society and establish communication.

Sponsorship can be done to create an image, to realize sales or to achieve many purposes. The main purpose here is that the sponsor and the recipient of the sponsorship gain mutual benefits. The purposes of sponsorship are to increase social awareness about the company, to reach the target market more effectively, to leave a positive image in those who make purchasing decisions, to enable media management and to realize sales targets [3]. In addition, sponsorship is the provision of resources (money, people, equipment) to an event or activity by a company in direct cooperation with the event or activity. The company that provides this resource tries to realize its marketing or media-related objectives. Sporting events have one of the highest target audiences in the world. There are millions of spectators who follow sports events both in stadiums, halls and on their screens. In this respect, sponsor companies prefer sponsorship in sports or advertising in sports in order to reach more target audiences.

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Inan stated that sports sponsorship is the most effective promotion activity that can be used to achieve marketing and goal objectives and that sports sponsorship has become the most preferred type of sponsorship by companies [4]. Sports competitions broadcast on TV and their viewership rates have become the focus of many companies and brands. For example, it is stated that 3.7 billion people watched the opening ceremony of the Sydney Olympics in 2000 live on TV [5], and nearly 4 billion people watched the London Olympics in 2012 [6]. The 2017 UEFA Champions League final match between Real Madrid and its rival Liverpool was watched live by 1.1 billion people from 200 countries, while 3.16 million people in China and 12 million people around the world watched Fenerbahçe's THY Euroleague final in the 2015-2016 season [7]. Therefore, the demand of sponsor companies to sponsor organizations watched by millions of TV viewers and audiences is increasing.

Within this framework, the concept of consumption in sport should be taken. According to economists, consumption is the direct consumption of goods and services to satisfy wants in order to create benefits. According to the marketing discipline, consumption is the satisfaction of demands and needs. One of the important suggestions for consumer behavior is that people buy products not because of their basic functions but because of their meaning [8]. The concept of consumption is discussed with the sub-dimensions of ostentatious consumption [8], symbolic consumption [9,10], compulsive consumption, hedonic consumption [11,12] and utilitarian consumption. In terms of the sport industry, spectators are consumers of sport. Sports consumers are considered as people who consume goods and services related to sports. The sports sector, on the other hand, acts with supply sources for its customers and shapes the supply according to their demands. The consumer sizes of active and passive spectators in sports differ and supply sources produce goods and services accordingly [13].

Importance of the Study

Sponsorship and advertising in sports are important in terms of providing financial resources for sports organizations, competitions and other activities. On the other hand, companies that try to create an image through advertising and sponsorship try to increase their recognition and awareness through sports competitions. In this context, it gains great importance which sports organization and which branches the companies necessary statistical analyzes were performed.

that want to make advertising and sponsorship should work for. From this point of view, in this study, which will be conducted to determine the perception levels of advertising and sponsorship activities in sports competitions by the audience and to determine the impact of the institutions sponsoring the sports branch on the audience, it is of great importance to determine the perception levels of the advertising and sponsorship activities presented during the television broadcasts of football, basketball, tennis and athletics competitions with high audience, and to determine which sports branch and organization the sponsoring companies should invest in according to the level of perception on the audience.

The main purpose of the research is to determine the recall levels of the audience for advertising and sponsorship practices in the broadcasts of sports competitions and to obtain theoretical data on sports sponsorship and advertising studies in terms of demographic variables.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study, which was conducted to determine the perception levels of advertising and sponsorship practices in football, basketball, athletics and tennis competitions broadcast on television, was designed as a descriptive research in categorical survey model. The survey model is a research model that aims to describe a past or ongoing situation as it exists [14]. The descriptive survey model is a model used to describe the structure and functioning of societies, objects, institutions and events.

The population of the study consists of all spectators who follow football, basketball, tennis and athletics competitions broadcast on television. The sample of the study consisted of 466 people who actively follow sports competitions and who were selected with the easily accessible method.

In addition to demographic information, data were collected with a simple questionnaire form (yes/no) developed by the researcher in order to determine whether the sample group could remember the advertising and sponsorship activities offered in the sports competitions they would watch after a while after the end of the competition.

2.1. Statistical analysis

In order to express the data obtained from the audience with numerical values, they were transferred to the computer environment and Before the analysis, normality test was performed

for the sample group and it was determined that the data were not normally distributed. Therefore, nonparametric tests were used. Therefore, in

addition to arithmetic mean (\bar{x}), frequency (f) values, chi-square test was applied and z test was used for row-column comparison.

3. RESULTS

Table 1. Percentage-frequency values of demographic information of the sample group

		f	%
Gender	Woman	158	33,9
	Male	308	66,1
Sport Branch	Football	347	74,5
	Volleyball	48	10,3
	Other	29	6,2
	Basketball	25	5,4
	Tennis	12	2,6
	Athletics	5	1,1
Age	Under 25 years old	184	39,5
	26-40	266	57,1
	41 and above	16	3,4
How many times do you watch a competition on TV in a month?	1-3	223	47,9
	4-6	110	23,6
	7-9	52	11,2
	10-12	23	4,9
	More	58	12,4
When was the last time you watched a competition on TV?	Just Before	210	45,1
	The Day Before	77	16,5
	One week ago	83	17,8
	About a horse ago	96	20,6
Approximately how much is your total monthly expenditure on sports?	Less than 100TL	268	57,5
	100-250TL	127	27,3
	250-500TL	48	10,3
	Over 500TL	23	4,9
Did you watch the competition live or on tape?	Live	372	80,2
	Tape	94	19,8
After watching a competition on TV, do you feel the desire to use/purchase the products of the companies you see advertised?	No.	336	72,1
	Yes	130	27,9
Do you follow the companies you see advertised in the competitions you watch on TV on social media?	No.	430	92,3
	Yes	36	7,7

As a result of the analysis made between the levels of recall of the athletes' jersey brands in the sports branch competitions followed by the spectators in the sample group, a significant difference was found between football and

volleyball branches in favor of football ($p=.047$, $p<.05$), while there was no significant difference ($p>.05$) between other sports branches (basketball, tennis, athletics) Table 2.

Table 2. Comparison results between the recall levels of jersey brands according to sports branches

Groups	Those who remember the jersey brand		Total	p
	Yes			
Football	80a		313	0,047
Basketball	5		24	
Tennis	2		11	
Volleyball	3b		42	
Athletics	1		4	
Other	3		28	
P<0,05				

Table 3. Comparison results of the recall levels of jersey brands according to the monthly frequency of watching competitions

Groups	Those who remember the jersey brand		Total	p
	Yes			
1-3	39		190	0,528
4-6	24		86	
7-9	12		39	
10-12	7		18	
More	12		30	
P<0,05				

There was no significant difference between the levels of recall of jersey brands according to the

number of competitions watched by the sample group.

Table 4. Comparison results of the recall levels of jersey brands according to gender variable

Groups	Those who remember the jersey brand		Total	p
	Yes			
Woman	23a		140	0,00
Male	71b		223	
P<0,05				

There was a significant difference between the participants' levels of remembering the brands of the jerseys in the competition they watched in

favor of men ($p=.00$, $p \leq 0$). In other words, it was concluded that male spectators remembered jersey brands at a higher rate than female spectators.

Table 5. Chi-square test results of the recall levels of jersey brands according to age categories

Groups	Those who remember the jersey brand		Total	p
	Yes			
Under 25 years old	31		133	0,00
26-40 years old	60		116	
41 and above	3		14	
P<0,05				

According to the results of the Chi-square test, although a significant difference was detected at the 0.05 level, no difference was detected

between those who remembered the jersey brand among different age categories.

Table 6. Chi-square test results of jersey brands according to total monthly expenditures for sports

Groups	Those who remember the jersey brand		Total	p
	Yes			
Less than 100TL	49		215	0,004
100-200TL	32		90	
250-500TL	6		37	
500TL and above	7		21	
P<0,05				

According to the results of the Chi-square test, although there was a significant difference at the .05 level, no difference was detected between

the total monthly expenditure levels. The source of the difference may stem from the data between the groups that do not remember.

Table 7. Comparison results of jersey brands according to the time of the last competition

Groups	Those who remember the jersey brand		Total	p
	Yes			
Just now	48a		137	0,00
The day before	16		61	
In about a week	17		72	
In about a month	13b		93	

P<0,05

There is a significant difference between the participants' level of recall of jersey brands according to the time of the last competition. It is

seen that the level of remembering the competition times of the spectators' decreases day by day.

Table 8. Comparison results of the audience's jersey brands according to whether they watched the live or taped broadcast

Groups	Those who remember the jersey brand		Total	p
	Yes			
Live streaming	81a		276	0,002
Tape broadcast	9b		79	

P<0,05

There was a significant difference between the participants' level of recall of jersey brands according to the variables of watching Live and

Tape broadcast in favor of Live broadcast (p=.002, P<0.05).

Table 9. Comparison results of shoe brands according to sports branches

Groups	Who remembers a shoe brand		Total	p
	Yes			
Football	66		275	0,442
Basketball	4		19	
Tennis	2		10	
Volleyball	4		40	
Athletics	1		4	
Other	4		23	

When the recall levels of the sports branches and shoe brands watched by the spectators were compared, no significant difference was found

according to the results of the Chi-square test (p=.442, P>0.05).

Table 10. Comparison results of shoe brands according to the number of monthly competition viewers

Groups	Who remembers a shoe brand		Total	p
	Yes			
1-3	25		180	0,001
4-6	18		89	
7-9	17		41	
10-12	9		18	
More	12		43	

P<0,05

According to the results of the comparison between the recall levels of shoe brands in terms of the number of sports competitions watched monthly by the sample group, a significant

difference was found (p=.001, p<.05). The source of the difference seen in the table is due to the data between the non-remembering groups.

Table 11. Comparison results of shoe brands according to gender variable

Groups	Who remembers a shoe brand		Total	p
	Yes			
Woman	17a		144	0,00
Male	64b		223	

P<0,05

According to the Chi-square test results, there was a significant difference between the levels of recall of shoe brands in the competitions

watched between genders in favor of men ($p=.00, p \leq 05$).

Table 12. Comparison results of those who remember shoe brands according to age variables

Groups	Who remembers a shoe brand		Total	p
	Yes			
Under 25 years old	32		136	0,527
26-40 years old	47		223	
41 and above	2		12	

No significant difference was found as a result of the comparison of the levels of remembering the shoe brands in the competitions

watched by the sample group according to the age variable ($p=.527, p > 05$).

Table 13. Comparison results of shoe brand recall according to total monthly expenditures for sports

Groups	Who remembers a shoe brand		Total	p
	Yes			
Less than 100TL	42a		221	0,001
100-200TL	34b		96	
250-500TL	5a,c		72	
500TL and above	0c		17	

P<0,05

A significant difference was found between the participants' level of recalling shoe brands according to the monthly expenditure variable. In other words, participants whose monthly expenditures for sports are less than 100 TL

(51.9%) are more likely to remember shoe brands than participants who spend more than 100 TL (42% 100-250TL, 6.2% 250-500, 0% 500 and above).

Table 14. Comparison results of shoe brands according to the last watched competition time

Groups	Who remembers a shoe brand		Total	p
	Yes			
Just now	38a		141	0,004
The day before	15		67	
In about a week	21		76	
In about a month	7b		87	

P<0,05

A significant difference was found when the levels of recall of shoe brands in the competition watched by the spectators were compared in terms of the time of watching the competition ($p=.004, p<.05$). When the results were compared, the

participants who watched the competition on time remembered the shoe brands 5.4 times better than the participants who watched the competition within a month.

Table 15. Comparison results of shoe brands according to whether they are watched as live or taped broadcast

Groups	Who remembers a shoe brand		Total	p
	Yes			
Live streaming	68		283	0,226
Tape broadcast	11		80	

There was no significant difference between the participants' levels of recalling the brands of

shoes in the competitions they watched in terms of watching live and tape broadcasts ($p=.226, p>.05$)

Table 16. Comparison results of edge advertisements according to sports branches

Groups	Those Who Remember Edge Ads		Total	p
	Yes			
Football	43		266	0,188
Basketball	0		18	
Tennis	3		11	
Volleyball	5		39	
Athletics	0		4	
Other	2		25	

There was no significant difference between the levels of recall of the edge advertisements according to the sports branches in the competitions watched by the sample group

($p=.188$, $p>.05$). In other words, there is no effect of sports branches on the level of remembering the edge advertisements in the competitions watched.

Table 17. Comparison results of sidebar advertisements according to the number of monthly competition viewers

Groups	Who remembers Edge ads		Total	p
	Yes			
1-3	18a		180	0,028
4-6	15		91	
7-9	7		35	
10-12	4		14	
More	9b		43	

$P<0,05$

A significant difference was found between the levels of recall of the side advertisements in the competitions watched by the sample group in terms of the number of competitions watched per month ($p=.028$, $p\leq 05$). It was found that the

participants who watched 1-3 competitions per month (34%) remembered the side advertisements 2 times more than the participants who watched 10-12 or more competitions (17%).

Table 18. Comparison results of sidebar ads according to gender variable

Groups	Who remembers Edge ads		Total	p
	Yes			
Woman	12a		142	0,00
Male	41b		221	

$P<0,05$

According to the Chi-square test results, there was a highly significant difference between the recall levels of the sideline advertisements in

the competitions watched between genders in favor of men ($p=.00$, $p\leq 05$).

Table 19. Comparison results of sidebar ads according to age variable

Groups	Who remembers Edge ads		Total	p
	Yes			
Under 25 years old	18		133	0,552
26-40 years old	35		216	
41 and above	0		14	

No significant difference was found as a result of the comparison of the levels of remembering the side advertisements in the

competitions watched by the spectators according to the age variable ($p=.552$, $p>.05$).

Table 20. Comparison results of sidebar ads according to total monthly expenditures on sports

Groups	Who remembers Edge ads	Total	p
	Yes		
Less than 100TL	31	207	0,505
100-200TL	15	99	
250-500TL	7	39	
500TL and above	0	18	

According to the results of the Chi-square test, there was no difference between the groups in terms of the variable of total monthly spending

money for sports between the levels of remembering the side advertisements during the competition broadcasts ($p=.505$, $p>.05$).

Table 21. Comparison results of sidebar advertisements according to the time of the last watched competition

Groups	Remember Edge ads	Total	p
	Yes		
Just now	25	143	0,466
The day before	9	63	
In about a week	10	76	
In about a month	9	81	

There was no significant difference between the recall levels of the side advertisements

according to the factor of the time of watching the competition ($p=.466$, $p>.05$).

Table 22. Comparison results of sidebar ads according to whether they are watched as live or broadcast

Groups	Remember Edge Ads	Total	p
	Yes		
Live streaming	58a	326	0,016
Tape broadcast	4b	75	

$P<0,05$

A significant difference was found between the participants' level of recall of edge advertisements according to the variables of watching live and taped broadcasts ($p=.0165$,

$p<.05$). When this situation is evaluated, it is determined that the live broadcast viewers have a higher recall rate than the viewers watching the tape broadcast.

Table 23. Comparison results of name sponsors according to sports branches

Groups	Remembering Name Sponsors	Total	p
	Yes		
Football	22	280	0,168
Basketball	1	21	
Tennis	0	11	
Volleyball	8	41	
Athletics	0	4	
Other	2	24	

There was no significant difference between the levels of remembering the name sponsors according to the factor of sport branches in the competitions watched by the spectators ($p=.168$,

$p>.05$). In other words, sports branches have no effect on the level of remembering the name sponsors in the competitions watched.

Table 24. Comparison results of name sponsors according to the number of monthly competition viewers

Groups	Remembering Name Sponsors	Total	p
	Yes		
1-3	7a	194	0,000
4-6	12b	92	
7-9	5b	40	
10-12	1	17	
More	8b	38	

P<0,05

According to the result of the comparison between the recall levels of the name sponsors in terms of the number of sports competitions watched monthly by the participants, a significant

difference was found in favor of the groups who watched the competitions more than 1-3 times (p=.000, p<.05).

Table 25: Comparison results of name sponsors according to gender variable

Groups	Remembering Name Sponsors	Total	p
	Yes		
Woman	9	148	0,00
Male	24	233	

P<0,05

According to the results of the Chi-square

test, there was no difference between the levels of recall of name sponsors between genders (p=.00, p<.05).

Table 26. Comparison results of name sponsors according to age variable

Groups	Remembering Name Sponsors	Total	p
	Yes		
Under 25 years old	13	139	0,978
26-40 years old	19	228	
41 and above	1	14	

No significant difference was found as a result of the comparison of the participants' levels of remembering the name sponsors in the

competitions they watched according to the age variable (p=.978, p>.05).

Table 27. Comparison results of name sponsors according to total monthly expenditures for sports

Groups	Remembering Name Sponsors	Total	p
	Yes		
Less than 100TL	18	225	0,009
100-200TL	15	98	
250-500TL	0	39	
500TL and above	0	19	

P<0,05

According to the results of the comparison, although a significant difference was detected, no difference was detected between the levels of remembering the name sponsors in terms of the

variable of monthly total expenditure on sports. The source of the difference is due to the data between the groups that do not remember

Table 28. Comparison results of title sponsors according to the time of the last competition watched

Groups	Remembering Name Sponsors	Total	p
	Yes		
Just now	12	145	0,029
The day before	8	66	
In about a week	8	76	
In about a month	5	94	

P<0,05

Although there was a significant difference between the sample group's level of remembering the name sponsors in the competition they watched according to the results of the comparison made in terms of the time of watching the

competition, it was determined that there was no difference between the groups. The source of the difference is due to the data between the groups that do not remember.

Table 29. Comparison results of sponsors according to whether they are watched live or as a live broadcast

Groups	Remembering name sponsors	Total	p
	Yes		
Live streaming	32	335	0,554
Tape broadcast	6	85	

There was no significant difference between the participants' levels of remembering the name sponsors in the competitions they watched

according to the results of the comparison made in terms of watching Live and Tape broadcasting ($p=.554$, $p>.05$).

Table 30. Comparison results of stadium names according to sports branches

Groups	Who remembers the names of the stadiums	Total	p
	Yes		
Football	116a	248	0,000
Basketball	7b	22	
Tennis	0c	9	
Volleyball	6	40	
Athletics	0	4	
Other	3	26	

$P<0,05$

As a result of the analysis made between the participants' levels of remembering the stadium names in the sports branch competitions followed by the spectators, a significant difference was

found between football, basketball and tennis branches in favor of football ($p=.000$, $p<.05$). There was no significant difference between other sports branches (volleyball and athletics) ($p>.05$).

Table 31. Comparison results of stadium names according to the number of matches watched per month

Groups	Who remembers the names of the stadiums	Total	p
	Yes		
1-3	47a	178	0,000
4-6	34b	77	
7-9	15	37	
10-12	9	16	
More	27c	41	

$P<0,05$

There was a significant difference between the levels of remembering the stadium names according to the factor of the number of matches watched ($p=.000$, $p<.05$). In other words, the

number of matches watched has an effect on the level of remembering the stadium names in the competition.

Table 32. Comparison results of stat names according to gender variable

Groups	Who remembers the names of the stadiums	Total	p
	Yes		
Woman	31a	137	0,00
Male	101b	318	

$P<0,05$

According to the results of the analysis between the levels of remembering the stadium names in the competitions watched between

genders, there was a highly significant difference in favor of men ($p=.00$, $p \leq .05$).

Table 33. Comparison results of stat names according to age variable

Groups	Who remembers the names of the stadiums	Total	p
	Yes		
Under 25 years old	49	123	0,631
26-40 years old	79	213	
41 and above	4	13	

No significant difference was found as a result of the comparison of the levels of remembering the stadium names in the

competitions watched by the spectators according to the age variable ($p=.631$, $p>.05$).

Table 34. Comparison results of stadium names according to total monthly expenditures on sports

Groups	Who remembers the names of the stadiums	Total	p
	Yes		
Less than 100TL	76a	208	0,007
100-200TL	44	92	
250-500TL	10	30	
500TL and above	2b	18	
P<0,05			

A significant difference was found between the participants' level of remembering the stat names according to their monthly expenditure on sports ($p=.007$, $p<.05$). In other words, it was seen

that participants who spent less than 100 TL remembered the stat names more than participants who spent 500 TL and above.

Table 35. Results for the comparison of stadium names according to the time of the last match watched

Groups	Who remembers the names of the stadiums	Total	p
	Yes		
Just now	71a	132	0,000
The day before	24	60	
In about a week	25	69	
In about a month	12b	88	
P<0,05			

A significant difference was found between the levels of recall of stadium names according to the factor of the number of matches watched by the spectators ($p=.000$, $p<.05$). In other words, the number of matches watched has a high effect on

the level of recall in competitions. It was observed that those who had just watched the matches remembered the stadium names more than those who had watched the matches within 1 month.

Table 36. Comparison results of the names of the stadiums according to whether they are watched live or as a live broadcast

Groups	Who remembers the names of the stadiums	Total	P
	Yes		
Live streaming	119a	264	0,000
Tape broadcast	13b	85	
P<0,05			

A significant difference was found between the participants' level of recall of edge advertisements according to the variables of watching live and taped broadcasts ($p=.000$,

$p<.05$). When this situation is evaluated, it is determined that the live broadcast viewers have a higher recall rate than the viewers watching the tape broadcast.

Table 37. Comparison results of advertisements between broadcasts in competitions according to sports branches

Groups	Those Who Remember Inter-Broadcast Commercials		Total	p
	Yes			
Football	14		295	0,499
Basketball	1		22	
Tennis	2		11	
Volleyball	2		40	
Athletics	0		4	
Other	0		28	

There was no significant difference between the participants' level of recalling the advertisements between the broadcast according to the factor of sport branches in the competitions watched ($p=.499$, $p>.05$). In other words, there is no effect of sport branches on the level of recall of

inter-broadcast advertisements in the competitions watched. Based on this result, it can be suggested that sports marketing experts should take this situation into consideration and carry out advertising and marketing activities on the basis of individual competitions.

Table 38. Comparison results of inter-broadcast advertisements in competitions according to the number of monthly competition viewers

Groups	Remembering Inter-Broadcast Ads		Total	p
	Yes			
1-3	9		201	0,055
4-6	4		95	
7-9	1		44	
10-12	2		18	
More	3		42	

$P<0,05$

When the recall levels of inter-broadcast advertisements were compared in terms of the number of sports competitions watched monthly

by the audience, no significant difference was found according to the results of the Chi-square test ($p=.055$, $p>.05$).

Table 39. Comparison results of inter-broadcast advertisements according to gender variable

Groups	Those Who Remember Inter-Broadcast Commercials		Total	p
	Yes			
Woman	4		150	0,002
Male	15		250	

$P<0,05$

Although there is a significant difference in the table, no significant difference was found according to the results of the comparison between the levels of recall of inter-broadcast

advertisements according to gender variables. The source of the difference in the table is due to the data between the non-recalling groups.

Table 40. Comparison results of interstitials in competitions according to age variable

Groups	Those Who Remember Inter-Broadcast Commercials		Total	p
	Yes			
Under 25 years old	5		148	0,432
26-40 years old	14		238	
41 and above	0		14	

According to the result of the comparison of the levels of remembering the inter-broadcast advertisements in the competitions

watched by the spectators according to the age variable, no significant difference was found ($p=.432$, $p>.05$).

Table 41. Comparison results of inter-broadcast advertisements in competitions according to total monthly expenditures on sports

Groups	Recall Search Ads	Total	p
	Yes		
Less than 100TL	10	234	0,044
100-200TL	9	107	
250-500TL	0	41	
500TL and above	0	18	

P<0,05

According to the results of the Chi-square test, although a significant difference was detected, no difference was detected between different levels of expenditures on sports and those who

remembered the inter-broadcast advertisements. The source of the difference is due to the data between the groups that do not remember.

Table 42. Comparison of interstitials in competitions according to the time of the last competition

Groups	Those Who Remember Inter-Broadcast Commercials	Total	p
	Yes		
Just now	6	152	0,001
The day before	6	71	
In about a week	6	82	
In about a month	1	95	

P<0,05

Although a significant difference was detected according to the Chi-square results, no difference was detected between the levels of recall of inter-broadcast advertisements in terms

of the time of the most recently watched competition. The source of the difference is due to the data between the non-recalling groups.

Table 43. Comparison results of subtitles in competitions according to sports branches

Groups	Those who remember the subtitles in competitions	Total	p
	Yes		
Football	27	291	0,025
Basketball	2	18	
Tennis	0	9	
Volleyball	2	40	
Athletics	0	4	
Other	0	28	

P<0,05

According to the results of the Chi-square test, although a significant difference was detected, no difference was detected between the levels of recall of subtitle advertisements in terms of the

most recently watched sports branch. The source of the difference is due to the data between the groups that do not remember.

Table 44. Results of subtitles in competitions according to the number of monthly competition viewers

Groups	Those who remember the subtitles in competitions	Total	p
	Yes		
1-3	6a	199	0,00
4-6	8b	86	
7-9	4	44	
10-12	4b	18	
More	9b	43	

P<0,05

A significant difference was found between the levels of remembering the subtitles in the competition broadcasts according to the factor of

the number of competitions watched by the spectators ($p=.00$, $p<.05$). In other words, the effect of the number of matches watched on the level of

remembering the subtitles in the competitions is high.

Table 45: Comparison results of subtitles in competitions according to gender variable

Groups	Those who remember subtitles in broadcasts	Total	p
	Yes		
Woman	4a	146	0,001
Male	27b	244	

P<0,05

According to the Chi-square test results, there was a significant difference between the

recall levels of the competitions watched between genders in favor of men (p=.001, p ≤05).

Table 46. Comparison results of subtitles in competitions according to age variable

Groups	Those who remember subtitles in broadcasts	Total	p
	Yes		
Under 25 years old	10	146	0,059
26-40 years old	21	232	
41 and above	0	12	

P<0,05

No significant difference was found as a result of the comparison of the participants' levels of remembering the subtitles in the broadcasts of

the competitions they watched according to the age variable (p=.059, p >05).

Table 47. Comparison results of subtitles in competitions according to total monthly expenditures on sports

Groups	Those who remember subtitles in broadcasts	Total	p
	Yes		
Less than 100TL	18a	236	0,000
100-200TL	13b	100	
250-500TL	0	35	
500TL and above	0	19	

P<0,05

A highly significant difference was found between the participants' recall levels of the subtitles in the broadcasts according to the monthly expenditure variable (p=.000, p<05). In

other words, participants spending less than 100 TL remembered the interstitials more than participants spending between 100-250 TL.

Table 48. Results of subtitles in the competitions according to the last watched competition time

Groups	Those who remember subtitles in broadcasts	Total	p
	Yes		
Just now	16	152	0,006
The day before	8b	70	
In about a week	4	72	
In about a month	3a	96	

A significant difference was found between the participants' level of remembering the subtitles in the broadcast according to the factor of the number of competitions watched (p=.006, p<05). In other words, the number of matches watched

has a high effect on the level of remembering the subtitles in the competitions. It was observed that those who watched the broadcast the day before remembered the subtitles more than those who watched the broadcast in approximately 1 month.

4. DISCUSSION

The aim of this research is to examine the recall levels of spectators for advertising and sponsorship practices in the broadcasts of sports competitions. In this section, the findings obtained in the research are discussed and discussed within

the framework of the sub-objectives determined and various conclusions are given.

In the market environment where competition is increasing day by day, businesses show differentiation efforts by getting support from the growing sports economy. In addition, businesses use marketing techniques related to

advertising and sponsorship practices in sports competitions to create or increase their brand value. One of the methods whose impact has recently been tried to be measured more and whose importance has been recognized in this way is advertising and sponsorship in sports competitions [15]. While sponsorship has traditionally placed much emphasis on 'visibility' measures, standard measures of brand awareness, recall and recognition have been borrowed from traditional advertising research [16]. Likewise, it is argued that through sport or sport sponsorship, consumers perceive different functions of advertising and develop a particular attitude towards advertising, which in turn increases their recall of a particular advertised or sponsored product [17]. Building consumer awareness is one of the critical objectives when entering into an advertising and sponsorship deal. This is because if the awareness of spectators' recall of advertising and sponsorship practices at sporting events is not achieved, sponsors will face more difficulties in achieving other downstream objectives such as image enhancement, influencing positive behavioral intentions and ultimately increasing sales [18,19]. Therefore, assessing advertising and sponsorship awareness among audiences from the sponsors' perspective is crucial for understanding the value and return on investment of sponsorship deals.

According to the z-test results covering the first sub-problem of the study, a highly significant difference was found (Table 4, Table 11, Table 18, Table 31, Table 44). Male spectators who participated in the research have higher levels of remembering jersey brands, remembering shoe brands, remembering the side advertisements in the competitions, remembering the name of the stadium where the competition is played and remembering the subtitles on the screens than female spectators. This result can be used as a preliminary market research about customer portfolios for jersey producers and companies that are considering to produce jerseys. In a study conducted by Yağcı and İlarslan [20], "The Effect of Advertisements and Gender Identity Role on Consumers' Purchasing Behaviors", one of the important results is that consumers' gender identity is an important factor in their reactions to advertisements. Therefore, the level of recall of advertising and sponsorship practices in sports competitions can be considered as a market research for shoe manufacturers and companies planning to become individual brand sponsors. Similarly, it has been observed that for the companies that are planning to give edge advertisements to the competitions and for the

companies that are planning to become competition sponsors by making a name agreement, the edge advertisements do not attract the attention of the female audience and the advertisements are not remembered by the female participants (Table 18). Based on this result, it can be suggested that sports marketing experts should take this situation into consideration and carry out advertising and marketing activities on the basis of individual competitions.

On the other hand, in our study, it was determined that the levels of remembering interstitial advertisements and name sponsors did not differ significantly in terms of gender according to the levels of remembering advertising and sponsorship practices applied in sports competitions broadcast on TV (Table 23, Table 38). Therefore, it can be concluded that companies that are planning to advertise during the inter-broadcast of competitions will not need to make advertising studies based on viewership rates.

In contrast to this study, when compared with Okumuş's [21], "The Effect of Advertising and Advertising on Consumer Preferences" study, it was concluded that consumers made a consumption preference under the influence of advertising in the context of gender, and this result determined that female consumers made more advertising-based product preferences than male consumers. Based on this result, it can be suggested that sports marketing experts should take this situation into consideration and carry out advertising and marketing activities on the basis of individual competitions. According to the results of the Chi-square test conducted to analyze the second sub-problem of the research, a significant difference was found in the variables of remembering the jersey brands and remembering the name of the stadium (Table 2., Table 29). This result will give ideas to jersey manufacturers that football jersey brands are more memorable than other branches and that advertising and promotional activities on football jerseys may be more meaningful and important.

Among the participants who participated in the study and remembered the jersey brands and stadium names, 196 of them follow the football branch. There are 7 participants who follow the basketball branch and remember the jersey brand and stadium name. There are 3 participants who follow the volleyball branch and remember the jersey brand and stadium name. When the test results are compared, it is found that the participants who follow the football branch have a higher level of sponsor recall than all other sports branches. In a study, Erdoğan and Kitchen [22], also examined the relationship between

sponsorship and advertising and concluded that both cannot be used interchangeably, but when they are used together, businesses benefit more. Ulu [23], reached a similar conclusion in his study titled "The Effect of Sports Sponsorship in Urban Areas on Consumer Behavior". On the other hand, no significant difference was found when the participants' levels of remembering shoe brands, remembering edge advertisements, remembering name sponsors, remembering interstitials and remembering subtitles were compared with the sport branch variable (Table 9., Table 16., Table 21, Table 36., Table 42.). In other words, there is no effect on the level of remembering the side advertisements in the competitions according to the time of watching the competition. Based on this result, it can be suggested that sports marketing experts should take this situation into consideration and carry out advertising and marketing activities on the basis of individual competitions.

According to the results of the Chi-square test conducted to analyze the third sub-problem of the research, a highly significant difference was found when the variables of remembering side advertisements, remembering name sponsors, remembering stadium names and remembering subtitles were compared with the number of competitions watched (Table 17., Table 22., Table 30., Table 43). This result will give ideas to uniform manufacturers that football uniform brands are more memorable than other branches and that advertising and promotional activities on football uniforms may be more meaningful and important. When the recall levels of the spectators who participated in the research were analyzed, an inversely proportional relationship was found. It was determined that the spectators who watched the competitions between 1-3 on average per month had higher levels of remembering the sponsorships in the competitions than the spectators who watched 10-12 and more competitions. When the rates of remembering the name sponsors and subtitles in the competitions were compared, it was determined that the spectators who watched 1-3 competitions remembered less advertisements and sponsorships than the spectators who watched 10-12 and more competitions.

There was no significant difference between the participants' level of recall of jersey brands, recall of shoe brands and recall of interstitial advertisements according to the number of matches watched per month (Table 3., Table 10., Table 37). In other words, the number of matches watched has no effect on the level of recall of jersey brands in competitions. Therefore, there is no need

for shoe manufacturers to carry out marketing and advertising activities based on viewing rates. On the other hand, based on this result, it can be suggested that sports marketing experts should take this situation into consideration and carry out advertising and marketing activities on the basis of individual competitions.

Alexandris et al. [24], tried to explain the relationship between the effects of sponsorship such as image creation, word of mouth advertising and purchase intention with attitude towards the sport event, participation in sport activities and beliefs about sponsorship. As a result of the study, it is seen that the relationship between the intention to purchase the sponsor brand, attitude towards the sport event and the dimensions of participation in sport activities is significantly satisfactory. In another study, Grohs [25], conducted an empirical investigation on the conditions affecting brand image development through sport event sponsorship. The study reviewed 30 years of literature on the brand image effects of sport sponsorship and 20 years of literature on the effects of sport sponsorship on brand image development. According to the findings, it is emphasized that there is a sponsorship relationship between the sponsoring brand and the sponsored sport event and that the sponsorship has a direct long-term effect on improving the image of the sponsoring brand.

Tan and Pyun [26], examined the effectiveness of sports sponsorship in the 2014 F1 Singapore Grand Prix. Tests of recall and recognition by viewers and the target audience as a result of the brands' logos on cars, drivers' clothes and venues were applied to undergraduate students. After watching a 30-second video, they were asked to respond to questionnaires. According to the results of the research, cars and drivers' clothes were found to be more effective places for brand recognition. The lack of evidence in assessing consumers' attitudes towards sports sponsorship and sports advertising may lead sports marketers to erroneous decisions when choosing a promotional tool. If there is no awareness of the levels of recall of advertising and sponsorships aired at competitions according to the frequency of competition viewing over a one-month period, sponsors will face more difficulties in reaching subsequent targets, which may ultimately lead to increased consequences. It can be argued that spectators who are more involved and invest time in a team are more likely to remember advertisements and sponsorships. However, it may be equal in duration but variable in magnitude and exclusivity. Therefore, it can be hypothesized that the dimension of exposure in

terms of duration are important variables that influence the attention of the audience to the level of recall of advertising and sponsorship practices in their competitions.

According to the results of the chi-square test conducted to analyze the fourth sub-problem of the research, no significant difference was found when the levels of remembering jersey brands, remembering shoe brands, remembering side advertisements, remembering name sponsors, remembering stadium names, remembering interstitial advertisements and remembering subtitles were compared with the age variable (Table 5., Table 12., Table 19., Table 24., Table 32., Table 39., Table 45.). Therefore, it can be suggested that there will be no need for marketing and advertising activities for different age groups. It can be suggested that companies considering to be the name sponsor of the clubs should plan their marketing activities by taking this into consideration.

As a result of the study conducted which included 85 academicians between the ages of 20-74, 46% of whom were male and 54% of whom were female, it was stated that the age factor had a negative effect on the level of recall of sponsors and the level of education had a positive effect on the level of recall of sponsors. In another study conducted by Alparslan [27], it was investigated whether there is a significant difference in the product preference of athletes according to the age variable among demographic components. It was concluded that the product preferences of the athletes participating in the study were more influenced by advertisements for those younger than 30 years of age. It was determined that this effect decreases as the age level increases. The results of the aforementioned study differ from this study. On the other hand, Okumuş [28], reported that the age variable did not show a significant difference between the groups. In a similar study conducted by Satır [29], no significant difference was found in any dimension in terms of age group variables regarding the effect of sponsorship on consumer attitude in sports clubs. This study supports the findings of this study. Therefore, it has been concluded that the companies that are thinking of giving inter-broadcast advertisements to the competitions and sponsoring subtitles to the channels will not need to make advertising studies based on the viewing rates according to the age variable. For this reason, producers can direct their sponsorship activities by considering this situation related to age factors while conducting market research of broadcasting organizations broadcasting competitions.

According to the results of the Chi-square

Test conducted to analyze the fifth sub-problem of the research, no significant difference was found when the levels of jersey brand recall, side advertisements recall, name sponsors recall, and intermediate advertisements recall were compared with monthly sports expenditures (Table 6., Table 20., Table 25., Table 40). In a similar study conducted by Satır [29], no significant difference was found in any dimension in terms of the monthly income status of the family regarding the effect of sponsorship on consumer attitude in sports clubs. Therefore, it can be argued that manufacturers and companies that are considering to be sponsors of jersey branding, side advertisements, name sponsors, and recall sponsors of interstitial advertisements do not need to make sports sponsorships based on monthly sports expenditures and recall levels of sports sponsorships.

However, when the levels of recall of shoe brands, recall of stadium names and recall of subtitles of the spectators participating in the study were compared with the variable of monthly sports expenditures, a highly significant difference was found between the recall of subtitles and monthly sports expenditures. In addition, a significant difference was found between the recall of shoe brands and the recall of stadium names and monthly sports expenditures. Considering the monthly sports expenditures of the spectators, it was determined that the participants who spent less than 100 TL remembered less sponsorships than the participants whose monthly sports expenditures were 500 TL or more. In a study conducted by Çiftçi [30], when the answers given to the statement "Sports sponsorship companies attract my attention" "I especially prefer the products of companies that sponsor the team I am a supporter of" "Sports sponsorship can make me prefer a product for the first time" were examined, it was found that there was a statistically significant difference in terms of personal net income. It was understood that participants with an income of 5001 TL and above agreed with this statement more. It is seen that similar results were reached in Özer's [31], study titled "The Effect of Attitude Towards Brand on Brand Image and Purchase Tendency after Sponsorship". In the study conducted by Tükenmez [32], significant differences were found in the dimensions of Interest Towards Football, Interest Towards Sponsors, Attitude Towards Sponsors and Club-Sponsor Compatibility for the monthly income variable. Therefore, it can be suggested that manufacturers and companies that are considering sponsorships based on the levels of recall of shoe brand, stadium names and subtitles

of the spectators can make sports sponsorships based on their monthly sports expenditures and recall levels of sports sponsorships.

According to the results of the Chi-square test conducted to analyze the sixth sub-problem of the research, a highly significant difference was found when the levels of jersey brand recall, shoe brand recall, stadium name recall and subtitle recall were compared with the time of watching the competition (Table 7., Table 14., Table 34., Table 47). Tan and Pyun [26], examined the effectiveness of sports sponsorship in the 2014 F1 Singapore Grand Prix. Tests of recall and recognition by viewers and the target audience as a result of the brands' logos on cars, drivers' clothes and venues were applied to undergraduate students. After watching a 30-second video, they were asked to respond to questionnaires. According to the results of the research, cars and drivers' clothes were found to be more effective places for brand recognition.

When the levels of jersey brand recall, shoe brand recall, and stadium name recall were analyzed, it was found that the participants who stated that they had just watched the sports competitions remembered the sponsorships better than the participants who stated that they had watched the sports competitions within a month. In addition to this, participants' recall levels of subtitles differ according to other sponsorship types. Participants who followed the competitions were found to remember the subtitles one day later, unlike other sponsorship types. Based on the time of watching the competitions in subtitle sponsorships, we can say that subtitle sponsorship is more memorable than other types of sponsorships. In this case, it can be said that the more exposure to the jersey brand, shoe brand, stadium names and sponsorship information, the higher the recall levels will be. Accordingly, in terms of time, it is assumed that sports consumers will perceive both sponsorship and advertisement positively, especially in the context of sports.

No significant difference was found between the participants' levels of recalling edge advertisements, name sponsorship and interstitial advertisements according to the time of watching the competitions (Table 4.21., Table 4.26., Table 4.41.). Therefore, it was concluded that sponsors would not need to carry out marketing and advertising activities regarding the levels of recalling edge advertisements, name sponsorship and interstitial advertisements according to the time of watching the competitions. Within the scope of analyzing the seventh sub-problem of the research, no significant difference was found between the levels of remembering shoe brands

and remembering the name sponsor according to the participants' status of watching the competitions live or broadcasted (Table 15., Table 27.). However, there was a highly significant difference between the levels of remembering jersey brands, remembering sideline advertisements and remembering stadium names when compared with the variable of watching the sports competitions live or via live broadcast (Table 8., Table 22., Table 35.). Therefore, there was a highly significant difference in remembering the jersey brands and stadium names in favor of the spectators who followed the competition from the live broadcast. However, it can be said that the spectators remembered the sideline advertisements less in live broadcasts.

Live broadcast viewing techniques assess memory and consumer preference for sponsorship [33] and recall and recognition are often used to track sponsor identity or awareness among research participants. Since one of the advantages of advertising is the ability to reach more consumers live via television than those attending the event [34], the number and duration of exposures may be important for consumers' ability to recall advertisements. Grohs et al. [35], found that exposure is a significant predictor of sponsor recall. In a study on virtual advertising and brand awareness, Cianfrone et al. [36], assessed the ability to recall brands in virtual ads and television commercials. It was observed that participants remembered the advertisements watched live at very high rates. The same study assessed the role of audience exposure to ads in live broadcasts on consumers' ability to recall and/or recognize advertised brands. It appears that exposure may have played a major role in this study, as it achieved high rates across all measures. Sports viewers also tend to frequently view or check the score screen during a televised sport. When this is considered, live viewers have a higher recall rate than viewers who watch a taped broadcast. Based on this result, it can be suggested that sports marketing experts should take this situation into consideration and carry out advertising and marketing activities on the basis of individual competitions.

5. Conclusion

It was concluded that the recall levels of the participants who followed the sports competitions showed a highly significant difference with all variables except the age variable, and the variables with the highest recall levels of the participants in stadium names were male participants remembered more stadium names. When the

variable of sports branches is considered, it is concluded that the most remembered stadium name is football, and there is a highly significant difference between the levels of recall of jersey brands and stadium names of people who watch the competitions live. When the levels of remembering the sponsorship practices encountered by the participants in the competitions they watched and the age variable are compared, it is seen that no significant difference is found with any type of sponsorship, and similar results are obtained when the levels of remembering the interstitial advertisements they watched in sports competitions are compared with other variables. It was concluded that there was a significant difference only between the number of competitions watched per month and the recall level of the side advertisements, while no significant difference was found with other variables. It was concluded that there was a significant difference between the level of recall of shoe brands of the spectators and the variable of monthly sports expenditures, but when asked about their willingness to buy the products they saw in the competitions, 72.1% of the participants answered no. When asked about the willingness of the spectators to follow the sponsoring companies on social media, it was concluded that 92.3% of the participants answered no. In conclusion, very little research to date has examined audience recall of advertising and sponsorship practices during broadcasts of sporting events. Specific to sport contexts, it can similarly be argued that consumers tend to have more positive attitudes towards advertising and sponsorship in sport contexts. It can be argued that audiences will perceive both sponsorship and advertising positively in sport contexts. Considering the limitations of this study, the following suggestions are offered for future research.

1. If the study is applied to a wider audience, important results can be reached in terms of sponsorship activities.
2. When sponsorship activities are carried out by considering the results found in the study, sponsorship activities that will attract the attention of female sports spectators can be sustained.
3. It can be a guide for companies or organizations considering sponsorship with sports clubs or companies to work on what kind of audience they can reach with which type of sponsorship.
4. The study can be conducted in a stadium with spectators watching the competition live.
5. The study can be conducted with members of a fan group to answer the question of whether the sponsoring companies were able to reach the desired audience.

In future studies, more comprehensive research can be conducted by adding more different variables

Conflict of Interest

No conflict of interest is declared by the authors. In addition, no financial support was received.

Ethics Committee

Data collection was initiated with the approval of Mersin University Social Sciences Research and Ethics Committee dated 10/01/2020.

Author Contributions

Study Design, UTO, DK; Data Collection, UTO, DK; Statistical Analysis, UTO, DK; Data Interpretation, UTO, DK; Manuscript Preparation, UTO, DK; Literature Search, UTO, DK. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript

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